

Comparative Study on Geopolymer Coated Recycled Aggregate Concrete

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Abstract:

At present India is witness to rapid development in all sectors leading to an increased need of new infrastructures at low cost and less time. Creation of new infrastructure deals with either demolition and repair of existing buildings or construction of new facilities altogether. However, demolition of buildings generates huge construction waste and new construction demand fresh conventional construction materials, production of which are associated with depletion of natural resources and emission of CO₂ and greenhouse gases. Since conventional and traditional construction materials like cement, coarse aggregate, fine aggregate, etc., are all obtained from natural resources by means of complex extraction procedures, a shortage in future availability is certain, Recycling and reusing of this concrete waste as alternate construction material not only will reduce the demand for natural resources but also minimize the area required for landfills and illegal dumping. But often the recycled aggregates obtained by crushing into desirable size is found to be contaminated with old mortar leading to disadvantages like relatively more water absorption, poor surface texture and formation of weak interface between aggregates compared to natural aggregate. To account for these disadvantages some recent studies have suggested the use of fly ash in the mix design. Hence, considering the variety of available of fly ash in India, a detailed comparative study is undertaken to understand the influence of characteristic properties of different fly ash on the performance of the various resulting compositions of recycled aggregates.

Keywords: Recycled Aggregate, Solid waste management, Recycling, Fly ash.

1. Introduction

India is currently experiencing fast development in all areas, which has boosted the demand for new infrastructure that can be built quickly and affordably. Developing new infrastructure generally, involves either demolishing and repairing existing structures or building brand-new facilities from scratch. However, both the methods come with their own set of repercussions. Demolition of structures produces a significant amount of construction debris mainly consisting of sand, gravel, concrete, stone, bricks, wood, metal, glass, plastic, paper, steel, etc, and are usually illegally dumped in landfills, roadside or natural water bodies resulting in environmental pollution. Solid waste generated due to construction and demolition activities is reported as 165–175 million tons between 2005 and 2013 (BMTPC 2018), and 530 million tons (Jain S. S Singhal and N. K. Jain, 2019) of which concrete waste forms 70%. Hence management of these construction and demolition waste has become a new challenge. On the other hand, new construction necessitates the use of natural conventional building materials, the manufacturing of which is linked to the depletion of natural resources and the release of various greenhouse gases and CO₂. Further, future scarcity in supply is unavoidable (Kamma R. C and Jha K. N, 2022) in view of the fact that these conventional and traditional construction materials such as cement, coarse aggregate, fine aggregate, etc. are sourced from natural resources via complicated extraction processes. Therefore, considering the definition of sustainability issued by World Commission on Environment and Development of the United Nations, i.e., “meeting the needs of the present without compromising the ability of the future generations to meet their own needs” (UNFCCC COP9 Rep. 2004), adoption of

greener sustainable alternative construction practices becomes imperative. In this context recycling and reusing this concrete waste as an alternative construction material has gained an increased attention in recent years and motivated numerous studies. As use of recycled aggregate will not only help in lowering the demand for natural resources, but will also solve the problems associated with space required for landfills and unlawful disposal. However, past studies have reported that the recycled aggregate usually obtained are found to be contaminated by residual adhered mortar, thus causing low specific-gravity and high water-absorption. These properties in turn contribute to increase of permeability and shrinkage, decrease in compressive strength and quality of concrete produced. Therefore, in order to use these recycled aggregate effectively a huge number of studies aimed at different aspects like utilizing them directly as sub-base material for pavement, improving their properties by removal of residual mortar (Tam et al., 2021), adding admixtures (Gull, I., 2011), adding industrial by-products like fly-ash (Gupta et al., 2012 ; Sarkar et al., 2005 and Das, S. K., & Yudhbir. , 2005), silica fume (Dilbas, H., 2014 and Akhtar et al., 2022), copper slag (Chithra et al., 2016), etc.; adding agricultural waste like rice husk (Padhi et al., 2018), biomass ash etc., have been undertaken.

However, considering the recent developments in the policies of the Indian government like Fly Ash notification 2021, constitution of a 'Fly Ash Management and Utilization Mission' and 'Pradhan Mantri Awas Yojana (Urban)' the handling and utilization of fly-ash from nearby thermal power stations have become imperative, hence opening a vast scope for research and development in Indian perspective. Adhering to the same objective the current study focuses on the utilization of fly ash as additive to recycled aggregate in order to improve the quality and performance of the resulting concrete.

Comparative Study on Fly Ash

Since the fly ash forms the main additive to improve the quality and performance of the resulting concrete in the present study, the basic understanding of the composition of fly ash is important. The origin of Indian coal being closely related to the characteristics of fly ash produced, forms one of the major causes of the variation of the fly ash, obtained from different thermal power plants accompanied by other factors like maintenance of the plant itself and quality management of the coal feed. Generally, considerable amount of intrinsic and extrinsic mineral matter is present in Indian coal, which is primarily of drift origin, thereby resulting in high ash content.

In order to get a qualitative idea of the variation of composition of the fly ash obtained in India, relevant data is collected from various past studies related to different National Thermal Power Corporation Limited (NTPC) plants and illustrated in Figure 1. The locations of plants are identified in order to cover the different geographical regions of India. Though total 106 thermal power plants are currently present in India, the study focuses only on the NTPC plants considering their presence in all region accompanied by better maintenance and quality control.

Fig. 1. Chemical composition of fly ash obtained from various sites of NTPC

From the Figure 1, it is very evident that the SiO₂ forms the major part of fly ash followed by Al₂O₃ and Fe₂O₃. As the reaction between these alumino-silicate components and calcium hydroxide results into additional cementitious materials, the higher the percentage of these components present in the fly ash the better it is. Therefore, from these understanding the fly ash from Farakka plant can be said to be most suitable. While the samples from other plants seems to have comparable composition indicating similar suitability.

Considering the observations from Figure 1, in order to check the effect of variation of fly ash composition in the strength of resulting mortar, results from past studies involving three plants namely, Dadri, Farakka and Mauda is studied and presented in Figure 2.

Fig. 2. Comparison of characteristic compressive strength of mortar using fly ash from various sites of NTPC

Referring to Figure 2, it may be noted, Farakka plant sample shows highest strength compare to other two plants. It may also be noted here that there are many other thermal power plants and coal quality varies from plant to plant. Therefore, fly ash properties varies from place to place. In our study fly ash from Bandel Thermal power station – West Bengal, is used.

Experimental Investigation

In order to understand the effect of presence of fly ash along with recycled aggregates, experimental studies on: (a) Uncoated Recycled aggregate concrete (RAC) (b) Geopolymer (composed of fly ash, NaOH solution and Sodium silicate) coated RAC and (c) Cement coated RAC, are conducted. The fly ash used is sourced from Bandel Thermal power station operated by WBPDCCL (West Bengal Power Development Corporation Limited). The Chemical composition of the fly ash used is given in Table 1 and the trial Mix proportions are presented in Table 2. Cubes of 70.6mm x 70.6mm x 70.6 mm were casted and water cured for 28 days.

An experimental study was also carried out to investigate the mechanical and micro-structural properties of RAC with uncoated and Geopolymer / Cement coated recycled aggregate exposed to elevated temperature. When making concrete, fly ash (in place of cement) was added. Temperatures of 450°C, 650°C, and 850°C were applied to test specimens for 5 hours with in muffle furnace. When exposed to different elevated temperatures, the compressive strength was reduced in the range of 20% to as much as 50%. The MIP (Mercury intrusion porosimetry) test was performed to estimate the pore diameter as well as to evaluate the change in total pore volume due to temperature changes.

Table 1. Chemical composition of the fly ash used

Chemical Properties	weight (%)
Silicon dioxide (SiO ₂)	60
Alumina (Al ₂ O ₃)	20
Calcium oxide (CaO)	8
Magnesium oxide (MgO)	1
Loss of ignition	8

Table 2. Trial Mix Proportion

Mix Designation	Cement	Fly ash	Sand	RAC	Water Binder ratio
M1 (RAC)	1	-	1.6	3.3	0.4
M2 (Geopolymer coated RAC)	0.9	0.1	1.6	3.3	0.4
M3 (Cement coated RAC)	1	-	1.6	3.3	0.4

*Proportions by weight

Results and Discussion

The results of the cube compressive test (as shown in Figure 3.) clearly indicates the better performance achieved due to coating of RAC with Geopolymer followed by cement coated RAC as compared to the normal RAC. This observation can be ascribed to the fact that the incorporation of fly ash leads to the modification of microstructure of the interfacial zone.

Fig. 3. Comparison of characteristic compressive strength of concrete obtained from trial mixes

Hence, to get better insight of the change in microstructure due to the presence of fly ash in geopolymer composition Mercury intrusion porosimetry test was performed (ref, to fig.4). The values of the total porosity for RAC and geopolymer coated RAC (GC-RAC) is obtained.

Lower value shown in case of geopolymer coated aggregate concrete, because of denser micro-structure observed through SEM. It explains the advantage of geopolymer coated aggregate concrete over uncoated RAC.

Fig. 4. Results of Mercury Intrusion Porisimetry (MIP)

Conclusion

Based on the present study, it can be concluded that the use of GC-RAC results in higher compressive strength. Based on the findings of this study, it is possible to conclude that using RAC with Geopolymer coating, produces a greater compressive strength. Also, its use leads to decreased porosity resulting from denser microstructure. The influence of source of fly ash reflecting in its composition and hence its performance is also changed. It may be noted here that there are many other thermal power plants and coal quality varies from plant to plant. As a result, the properties of fly ash vary depending on location. When exposed to different elevated temperatures, GC-RAC demonstrated higher compressive strength than uncoated RAC and cement coated RAC. In the case of coated RAC, fly ash replaces 10% of the cement, may be made. It outperformed coated RAC without fly ash in terms of strength. After being exposed to elevated temperatures, the porosity of GC-RAC (without fly ash) is lower than that of uncoated RAC (with fly ash) exposed to the same temperature level. At different temperatures, the compressive strength of recycled-aggregate concrete with geopolymer coated aggregate and cement coated aggregate is comparable. At both unheated and heated conditions, the microstructure of GC-RAC with fly ash is denser than that of uncoated RAC with fly ash.

Finally, it may be said that RAC with fly ash based geopolymer coating not only supports green technology concepts but also provides better performance compare to conventional concrete at lower cost and good waste management.

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